

Bikeability of road segments: An open, adjustable and extendible model

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
Bikeability
Infrastructure suitability
Cycling quality
Traffic stress
OpenStreetMap
GIS model

ABSTRACT

Providing adequate infrastructure for cycling is crucial for increasing its modal share and for supporting the shift towards sustainable mobility. To foster well-targeted, efficient, and effective improvements of infrastructure in favor of cycling, we need data and methods for assessing its current state in an automated, scalable, and reproducible way. Present models are limited due to dependency on proprietary and/or scarce data, being closed-source and not taking into account the many nuances of bikeability on segment scale. Therefore, we propose an open, adjustable, and extendible model of bikeability that relies on open and globally available data sets. It allows to consider aspects of safety, comfort, and the immediate environment. Results from an evaluation study show its applicability while underlining the importance of considering diversity in regional, individual, and purpose-related mobility demands. Future bikeability research may be informed by results of the online survey conducted as part of the evaluation study. The proposed bikeability model can form the foundation for advanced network and accessibility analysis and serves as an important information layer for decision making.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Safety, attractiveness and overall suitability of the transport infrastructure and its immediate surroundings are known to be crucial for enabling and promoting cycling mobility (Sottile et al., 2019). Active mobility is a key component for solution strategies to the diverse challenges of climate change, livability in urban areas, and public health. Consequently, research on bikeability has gained momentum in recent years. Bikeability metrics lay the foundation for numerous methods relevant to urban and transport planning. They enable accessibility analysis, support evidence-based prioritization of infrastructure interventions, and foster continuous and systematic monitoring.

Despite the term bikeability being commonly used in research as well as in practice, numerous definitions of what exactly bikeability captures exist (Kellstedt et al., 2021). Definitions vary in the scale of assessment and level of detail, in the methods used, and in the aspects that are regarded. They range from detailed assessment of individual road segments (e.g. Arellana et al., 2020; Karolemeas et al., 2022; Santos et al., 2022) or intersections (e.g. Beura et al., 2021) to neighborhood- or city-wide joint metrics (e.g. Kamel et al., 2020; Psarrou Kalakoni et al., 2022; Wysling and Purves, 2022). Some consider aspects such as cycling

demand and accessibility of facilities (Hamidi et al., 2019; Hardinghaus et al., 2021; Munira et al., 2021; Wysling and Purves, 2022), while others are descriptive of provided infrastructure and its surrounding environment (Pais et al., 2022; Schmid-Querg et al., 2021; Tijana et al., 2023). Tools for assessing bikeability may rely on objectively measurable aspects (e.g. Porter et al., 2019) or can be based on perceptions and sensations of individuals (e.g. Wesener et al., 2021). Some combine both approaches (e.g. Hagen and Rynning, 2021).

The existence of such a variety of concepts and methods leads to a lack of common understanding regarding the bikeability concept. It leaves a gap for standardized methods which enable comparability of assessments (Kellstedt et al., 2021). Castañon and Ribeiro (2021) and Kellstedt et al. (2021) present a more detailed review of available bikeability concepts and tools. These concepts have in common some form of assessment of the available mobility infrastructure and to some extent its immediate surroundings. In cases where this only represents part of the bikeability concept, it is sometimes referred to as “level of service” (Highway Capacity Manual, 2010), “cycling quality” (Grigore et al., 2019) or “bike suitability” (Lowry et al., 2012; Wysling and Purves, 2022).

Attempts to quantify the suitability of infrastructure elements (intersections and road segments) have already been undertaken by Sorton and Walsh (1994) with their “bicycle stress level”, which only

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcjr.2024.100040>

Received 29 February 2024; Received in revised form 25 June 2024; Accepted 24 July 2024

Available online 30 July 2024

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considered three variables: traffic volume, speed limit and lane width. The *Highway Capacity Manual (2010)* introduced “bicycle level of service (BLOS)”, which uses ten variables. However, [Callister and Lowry \(2013\)](#) found that data requirements of this method are hard to meet in practice. [Mekuria et al. \(2012\)](#) established the “level of traffic stress (LTS)” classification which refers to the four “types of cyclists” defined by [Geller \(2009\)](#). Besides such segment-based approaches, e.g. [Krenn et al. \(2015\)](#) developed a cell-based assessment for Graz in Austria, which regards the relative coverage of bicycle infrastructure, natural features, among others, per raster cell. [Codina et al. \(2022\)](#) also propose a raster-based approach using ten GIS-based variables.

Present bikeability models commonly utilize a (weighted) additive function to derive a single, non-standardized numeric index from individual attributes ([Castañon and Ribeiro, 2021](#)).

Many implementations are closed source. A prominent example of proprietary approaches is BikeScore® ([Redfin Corporation, n.d.](#); [Winters et al., 2016](#)). Such methods lack independent validation and are inherently limited in transferability, adaptability, and wider application.

The method by [Grigore et al. \(2019\)](#) considers segment-based attributes such as bicycle infrastructure, gradient, presence of specific hazards as well as attractiveness of the surroundings. However, it requires data on traffic volume, widths of bicycle infrastructure, and detailed aspects such as curb heights and distance of bicycle infrastructure to longitudinal parking. Furthermore, transferability and applicability are limited due to the source code not being available.

An example of bikeability models based on open data is by [Hardinghaus et al. \(2021\)](#). However, this method uses aggregation of OSM-based indicators to grid cells with binary classification (e.g. availability of any type of bicycle infrastructure). It does not consider distinct levels of suitability. Furthermore, the data and code are not freely accessible ([Hardinghaus et al., 2021](#)).

A noticeably open and transparent model was developed by [Wysling and Purves \(2022\)](#). All required data and code are available online. However, their “bike suitability” measure only regards seven fixed combinations of speed limit and bicycle infrastructure and is only defined for urban cases with maximum speed of 50 km/h. The only additional indicator is gradient, which is regarded in the routing stage ([Wysling and Purves, 2022](#)).

1.2. Research gap and objectives

From the literature review we identified segment-based bikeability as a commonly utilized measure that is central for informing various methods. It captures higher level of detail than cell-based assessments but can easily be aggregated to zonal metrics. Motivated from the application context in planning, we define bikeability as the suitability of transport infrastructure and its immediate surroundings for everyday cycling for the context of this work. While intersections are important to consider for enabling continuity in cycling networks, we only regard the single road segment (or edge in a network) as spatial reference unit. This decision is made due to limited availability of detailed data on intersection designs as well as a lack of consistent evidence on suitability of specific intersection designs. For example, OpenStreetMap data currently does not provide information on temporal sequences, traffic light timing, right of way, and the design of lane crossings.

From review of the literature, we found several gaps in bikeability metrics, which we address in this work. First, commonly applied bikeability metrics either regard a small subset of relevant aspects only or depend on data which are hard to acquire if available at all at global scale. Furthermore, only a few methods make use of open data and are freely available and adjustable themselves. There is a need for more customized definitions of bikeability that consider individual preferences towards cycling (e.g. for vulnerable groups such as children) and different types of bicycles ([Kellstedt et al., 2021](#)). Therefore, flexibility and transparency of the method are essential. The research gap becomes evident when regarding all of these aspects in combination.

Additionally, segment-scale bikeability metrics lack systematic validation ([Kellstedt et al., 2021](#)).

Based on these gaps, we defined the following objectives for the presented bikeability model:

- The method must be applicable to large spatial extents.
- Results must be comparable across cases.
- Consequently, input data and processing methods need to facilitate automation and reproducibility.
- It should be based on open and globally available data sets to ensure model applicability for various stakeholders.
- Network attributes should be enriched with spatial context to integrate the immediate surroundings into analysis.
- The method should allow additional data sets to be added without changes to the model logic.
- The model must remain stable in its design, robust towards missing values, and open for alternative data sets.
- Parameters need to be customizable to support modelling individual cycling preferences.
- An implementation of the model should be freely available and extendable. Therefore, open-source software is to be utilized.

We define the research question for this work as follows:

How and to what degree can we quantify segment-based bikeability from open data with a reproducible, transparent, and customizable approach?

2. Method

2.1. Bikeability model

Following the objectives outlined in [Section 1.2](#), we developed a segment-based model for bikeability which is implemented as an automated workflow in open-source software.

Our model is designed following the descriptive guidelines by [Loidl and Zigel \(2014\)](#). They outline a GIS-based workflow to derive quantitative indicators of cycling safety serving as abstraction layer from input data. Indicators were chosen following an iterative, knowledge-based approach in a local context. We built upon this descriptive methodological foundation and first building blocks, which meet several objectives defined in [Section 1.2.](#), and generalized it into a formal, parametric computational model. Options to include further indicators were gradually added to enable addressing additional aspects of safety, comfort, and environment. Furthermore, we now provide a default parameter set for generic bikeability assessment, targeting everyday cycling. Indicator selection as well as model parametrization followed the approach outlined in [Loidl and Zigel \(2014\)](#). This involved iterative refinement and adjustment based on scientific literature, knowledge of local experts in planning, and user feedback.

The model supports indicators that are inferred from both common network attributes, and spatial context using GIS methods. These indicators can be generated from various input data sets and thereby form an abstraction layer. Computation of the bikeability index takes place in a two-stage process with customizable parametrization. First, attribute values for each indicator are mapped to numerical values within unit interval $[0,1]$. Then, a weighted average is computed across all indicators to determine the joint bikeability index. We chose to use a weighted average to enable relative weighting of indicators while maintaining unit interval for the resulting metric. This is in line with the general logic of mostly (weighted) additive models in present literature.

We decided not to normalize attribute values relative to input data. Instead, we apply a consistent, absolute value mapping. This allows for comparing bikeability values across different areas of interest and assessment tasks. We define edge-based bikeability $b(e)$ for each edge e in a graph consisting of vertices and edges $G(V, E)$ as

$$b(e) = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n w_k i_k(e)}{\sum_{k=1}^n w_k}$$

for $e \in E$ and n indicators, where w represents indicator weight and i refers to numerical indicator value.

Since a weighted average might not adequately represent bikeability for certain indicator combinations, we allow rule-based overrides. This increases flexibility for modelling individual perspectives on bikeability. By default, we increase weights of gradient and surface for steep gravel segments. This is to represent the high risk and discomfort of such situations.

The proposed default bikeability profile considers the following reduced set of indicators: road category, bicycle infrastructure, maximum speed, gradient, type of pavement and designated bicycle route. Road category serves as proxy for traffic volume due to data availability. These six core aspects that represent primarily aspects of safety and comfort, default attribute value mappings, and indicator weights are presented in Table 1. Relevance of the chosen core indicators is supported by scientific evidence: presence and type of bicycle infrastructure (Buehler and Dill, 2016; Yang et al., 2019), aspects of designated bicycle routes (Lee, 2014), traffic volume (Broach et al.,

2012; Buehler and Dill, 2016), speed of motorized traffic (Buehler and Dill, 2016; Mertens et al., 2017), pavement (Hardinghaus and Weschke, 2022), gradient (Broach et al., 2012; Yang et al., 2019).

With the evaluation study presented in this work, suitability of the default bikeability profile is assessed within an international context. Key findings and points for future research and model improvement are presented in Section 4.

The full set of presently available indicators is presented in Appendix A.

Most indicators are derived from OpenStreetMap data which supports the objectives of automation and transferability outlined in Section 1.2. All necessary steps for network preprocessing and for deriving indicators are implemented in the open-source software NetAScore which is available on GitHub (Werner et al., 2024). Computation of gradient (steepness) is based on a digital elevation model (DEM) which can be added as optional data set. DEMs are widely available as open government data. If available, additional data may be added to enrich the bikeability index. As of early 2024, our implementation allows for adding traffic noise polygons to derive noise exposure. Further data layers may be added by adapting the source code. We provide all code together with the default “mode profile” that defines all parameters used to compute bikeability for this work in NetAScore V1.0.1 (Werner et al., 2024).

Table 1
Aspects, indicators, indicator values and their numerical mapping and weighting (default bikeability profile).

aspect of interest	indicator (observable, data item)	attribute values with default numerical mapping	default data source	default weight	remarks
availability and type of bicycle infrastructure	bicycle infrastructure	bicycle way: 1 mixed way: 0.9 bicycle road: 0.85 cyclestreet: 0.8 bicycle lane: 0.75 shared bus lane: 0.75 shared lane: 0.5 undefined: 0.2 no infra: 0	OpenStreetMap network geometry with attributes	0.2	
signage, wayfinding, awareness of motorized traffic, min. level of quality	designated bicycle route	international: 1 national: 0.9 regional: 0.85 local: 0.8 unknown route: 0.8 no route: 0	OpenStreetMap cycle networks	0.1	
traffic volume and potentially the share of HGV (heavy goods vehicles)	road category	primary: 0 path: 0 secondary: 0.2 residential: 0.8 service: 0.85 traffic calmed: 0.9 no motorized traffic: 1	OpenStreetMap network geometry with attributes	0.3	Please note: separated bicycle infrastructure parallel to e.g. a primary road will not bear the ‘primary’ attribute
speed limit (of motorized traffic)	max. speed	≥ 100 km/h: 0 ≥ 80 km/h: 0.2 ≥ 70 km/h: 0.3 ≥ 60 km/h: 0.5 ≥ 50 km/h: 0.6 ≥ 30 km/h: 0.85 > 0 km/h: 0.9 0 km/h: 1	OpenStreetMap network geometry with attributes	0.1	
surface quality	pavement type	asphalt: 1 gravel: 0.75 soft surface: 0.4 cobble stone: 0	OpenStreetMap network geometry with attributes	0.1	weight is increased in case of gravel combined with steep gradient
steepness of the road or path: safety aspects and physical effort needed	gradient (difference in elevation between nodes of each edge)	≥ 12 %: 0 < 12 %: 0.25 < 6 %: 0.4 < 3 %: 0.5 < 1.5 %, > -1.5 %: 0.9 > -3 %: 1 > -6 %: 0.95 > -12 %: 0.35 ≤ -12 %: 0	OpenStreetMap network geometry and digital elevation model (DEM)	0.1	[optional] weight is increased in case of gravel combined with steep gradient

For further details and explanation of indicator values please refer to the online documentation of [NetAScore](#)

2.2. Evaluation

We evaluated the applicability of the model and the soundness of its outputs through a two-stage study: an online survey and an on-site conference workshop with experts in cycling research. This approach was chosen to acquire quantitative as well as qualitative reference data and feedback. We based both parts of the study on the assessment of street-level imagery. The quantitative part focused on participants' perception of bikeability in comparison to results of the bikeability model. The qualitative assessment targeted at identifying reasons for participants' bikeability perceptions and at finding causes for the differences between perceived and modelled bikeability. Furthermore, we wanted to identify additional aspects that might be relevant but not yet included in our model.

Results of the evaluation study are presented in [Sections 3.2 and 3.3](#).

2.2.1. Data basis and image sampling

We selected the cities of Salzburg, Austria, and Wuppertal, Germany, as test cases. Both areas were defined as the bounding rectangle of their administrative boundary with a 1 km spatial buffer. With this approach, we capture a high variety of infrastructure in both areas. They consist of urban centers, urban periphery, and more rural areas. We acquired OpenStreetMap data using the Overpass Turbo API ([Raifer, n.d.](#)) on October 9, 2023. For Salzburg, a 10 m spatial resolution DEM ([Land Kärnten - data.gv.at, 2019](#)) was obtained and for Wuppertal we resampled the 1 m DEM by [Open.NRW, \(2023\)](#) to 5 m. With these inputs we computed bikeability using the default profile in NetAScore V1.0.1 ([Werner et al., 2024](#)) which utilizes the six core indicators outlined in [Section 2.1](#).

To enable image sampling based on levels of similar modelled bikeability, we grouped road segments into five distinct classes: very unbikeable [0,0.2], unbikeable (0.2,0.4], moderate (0.4,0.6], bikeable (0.6,0.8] and very bikeable (0.8,1].

Per study area we randomly sampled 25 road segments per bikeability class, on which cycling is legally allowed. We then obtained the most recent non-panoramic street-level image from Mapillary ([Mapillary, n.d.](#)) for each of the sampled segments, summing up to 250 images in total. We did a manual quality check of the obtained images and removed images for one or more of the following reasons:

- The image was not sharp.
- The image was largely covered by a car dashboard, rearview mirror, or windshield wiper.
- The image was not centered on the road segment itself.
- The image showed multiple road segments without it being clear which of them was the one of interest.
- The image showed a road segment which was obviously not accessible by bicycle, e.g. a motorway or hiking trail.

Following these criteria, we removed 143 images, leaving 107 suitable images. From these, 10 images per bikeability class were randomly sampled to be included in the survey. Of the remaining images, an additional 10 were selected manually because they showed especially interesting situations for bikeability assessment, such as a traffic calmed street or a painted bike lane. That is, a total of 60 images formed the final selection. For improved usability we cropped images to the relevant content, and adjusted brightness and contrast.

A detailed description of the sampling process as well as scripts to reproduce the workflow are available online at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10724361>.

2.2.2. Online survey

Using the full set of 60 street-level images, we designed an online survey asking for participants' bikeability ratings. We randomly subsampled 10 images per survey page, presenting two images per bikeability class. The manually selected set of images formed a page on its

own. In total, we offered 6 pages showing street-level images. The order of images per page was randomized for each participant. We kept the order of pages fixed but allowed participants to skip to the end of the survey at the bottom of each page. This ensured high response rates for images presented on the first pages, with gradually increasing drop-outs for consecutive pages. Each image was entitled with the question: "How suitable is this infrastructure for everyday cycling?". We provided a slider control below each image to give participants a continuous rating scale ranging from "very unsuitable" to "very suitable". To ensure good usability across devices, we enlarged interactive controls beyond visual UI elements. With this, the slider could easily be handled also on mobile devices with small screens and touch input. [Fig. 1](#) shows an exemplary question of the survey.

Beyond image-based bikeability ratings, we only posed a few additional questions. In the first survey section, we addressed cycling experience and attitude based on the four "types of cyclists" by [Geller \(2009\)](#), followed by brief demographic questions (country and place of residence, and optionally year of birth and gender). Subsequently to bikeability ratings, participants could optionally leave qualitative explanatory feedback, remarks on uncertainties as well as open comments before submitting the survey.

We implemented the survey using a LimeSurvey instance hosted by the University of Salzburg, and shared the invitation within our professional networks, through university newsletters and at conferences.

2.2.3. Expert workshop

The second part of the evaluation study was formed by an expert workshop. Here, we focused on fewer examples with more in-depth, qualitative feedback. For this purpose, we chose the CRBAM (Cycling Research Board Annual Meeting) conference which took place in Wuppertal, Germany from October 25–27, 2023. With a total of 131 participants from 19 countries ([Bergische Universität Wuppertal, 2023](#)), it brought together a substantial number of international experts in cycling research.

For the workshop, we had two main objectives: First, we wanted to enable in-depth discussions on exemplary infrastructure situations, collect quantitative bikeability ratings, and focus on qualitative assessments. This can be regarded as bottom-up inference, learning from the given examples. Second, we aimed at discussing the model definition, respectively its indicators, with the experts. This represents a more top-down approach to model evaluation.

To facilitate in-depth discussions, we limited the selection of street-level images to five – one per bikeability class. We sampled them randomly from survey images of the Wuppertal study area. Workshop participants were invited to have a seat at one of five tables, each presenting one street-level image. They were invited to discuss each example case for approximately five minutes in small groups and to note down their ratings as well as qualitative feedback. After each round of discussion, participants moved to the next example case. We integrated the discussion, quantitative and qualitative feedback regarding indicator selection as additional station into the interactive workshop concept. Consequently, six stations were offered in total which could be completed within approximately 30 minutes.

The quantitative bikeability assessment was designed similar to the online survey. We used the same question ("How suitable is this infrastructure for everyday cycling?") and a continuous scale. As analog implementation of the interactive slider, participants received adhesive dots they could place along a scale printed beneath the street-level image. This part of the assessment was also open to other conference participants after the workshop. For qualitative assessment we invited workshop participants to add aspects that positively or negatively influenced their bikeability rating using paper cards. We also instructed participants to note down aspects of uncertainty – e.g. in cases of crucial information not being visible from the street-level imagery.

Indicator assessment followed the same structure as bikeability ratings. Each indicator had an accompanying scale on which participants

Fig. 1. Exemplary survey question for bikeability ratings based on street-level imagery.

could rate its importance. Furthermore, we encouraged participants to add and subsequently rate indicators they thought were missing using blank rating scales.

3. Results

We divide the presentation of results into three subsections. The first part details on bikeability assessments for two study areas. The second part presents results from the online survey and the third section focuses on results from the expert workshop. Discussion of the results follows in Section 4.

3.1. Model results: bikeability

We computed segment-based bikeability following the method outlined in Section 2.1 using the core set of six indicators for two study areas in central Europe. These areas cover various types of land use, built-up density, and topography. All bikeability values shown in this first section represent the average of the forward (ft) and backward (tf) directions per network edge. All metrics are derived from input data described in Section 2.2.1. The metrics we provide in this section are merely descriptive of the segment-based bikeability index.

3.1.1. Salzburg, Austria

The network extracted for Salzburg, Austria covers an area of approximately 189 km² and has a total length of 2560 km. For 89 % of the network length no dedicated bicycle infrastructure is available. Mixed pedestrian and bicycle ways are the major form of bicycle infrastructure provided. 21 % of the network have good or very good bikeability, while 15 % provide bad or very bad bikeability. Further details are provided in Fig. 2 and Table 2.

3.1.2. Wuppertal, Germany

For Wuppertal the area covers 549 km² with a total network length of 7183 km. 93 % of the network does not provide any type of designated bicycle infrastructure. Mixed pedestrian and bicycle ways are the typical infrastructure provided. 13.2 % of the network have good or very good bikeability, while 12.8 % have bad or very bad bikeability. Details are shown in Fig. 3 and Table 2.

3.2. Online survey

We launched the online survey on October 25, 2023, and considered all responses until January 15, 2024. Out of 204 survey visits 152 full submissions were registered, resulting in a completion rate of 75 %. With 69 %, the majority of respondents are male, while 28 % identify as female and 2 % as non-binary. 72 % of participants feel best represented as “Enthusied and Confident” cyclists, followed by 20 % “Strong and Fearless”. 8.5 % see themselves as “Interested but Concerned”. Most respondents are based in Austria (45 %), followed by Germany (18 %), the Netherlands (6 %), the USA (5 %), Denmark (5 %), the UK (4 %), Switzerland (4 %), and France (3 %). The remainder is distributed across seven additional countries. As we allowed participants to quit the survey page by page, response rates gradually decreased from 76 % for page 2–20 % for page 6. 55 % participated in rating at least half of the 60 images available.

For compatibility with modelled bikeability, we re-scaled image-based ratings to unit interval [0;1]. Median ratings of the images range from 0.0 to 0.95 with a mean of 0.469. Overall, there is large variation in participants’ bikeability ratings per image. While the degree of dispersion varies between images, no pronounced differences are visible between bikeability classes. Still, on average dispersion is slightly higher for classes 2 and 4 and the lowest for class 5, as shown in Table 3.

Fig. 2. Segment-based bikeability for Salzburg, Austria.

Table 2
Key statistics for both study areas. Relative values refer to network length.

	Salzburg, Austria	Wuppertal, Germany
Area covered [km ²]	189	549
Network length [km]	2560	7183
Network density [km/km ²]	13.55	13.07
Average segment length [m]	47.7	48.7
Road type [%]		
Service	44.0	46.0
Residential	25.7	23.0
Non-motorized	15.1	17.8
Path	9.1	5.2
Primary	2.7	2.1
Traffic calmed	1.8	1.5
Secondary	1.7	4.5
Bicycle infrastructure [%]		
No dedicated	89.1	93.3
Mixed pedestrian and bicycle way	8.7	5.3
Bicycle lane	1.03	0.7
Bicycle way	0.74	0.6
Shared lane	0.19	0.02
Bicycle road	0.15	0.02
Shared bus lane	0.14	0.02
Access [%]		
Bicycle	82.7	77.1
Car	66.5	60.7
Bikeability [%]		
Very good	7.0	3.4
Good	14.9	10.6
Medium	62.3	72.4
Bad	11.8	11.5
Very bad	4.0	2.1

Bikeability ratings for all survey images are summarized in Fig. 4. It also includes modelled bikeability as reference markers (red lines).

More detailed plots that include the images shown are provided in Appendix B.

3.2.1. Modelled bikeability compared to image ratings

Modelled bikeability shows a strong positive correlation with median values of image-based ratings for the corresponding road segments. The Pearson correlation coefficient is 0.779 and Spearman’s ρ equals to 0.778. The mean absolute error (MAE) is 0.15. Fig. 5 shows the median of ratings in relation to modelled bikeability. However, statistical dispersion of ratings is not captured in this visualization. Therefore, we refer to Fig. 4 for a more detailed assessment.

For 56.7 % of samples modeled bikeability is within interquartile range (IQR) and for 80 % within interdecile range of respective image ratings. 70 % are within the mean absolute deviation.

When binning median ratings as well as modelled bikeability into five classes of equal interval, 40.0 % of cases are perfectly matched, and a total of 86.7 % are within a tolerance of maximum one class. Overall, the class of modelled bikeability is lower than the class of median reported bikeability in 23.3 % of cases and higher in 36.7 % of cases. With a reduced 3-bin classification, 61.7 % are matched, with 8.3 % being under- and 30.0 % being over-estimated. Using a binary classification (bikeable / unbikeable), in 86.7 % of the samples modelled and median rated bikeability match. All details are presented in Table 4.

Fig. 3. Segment-based bikeability for Wuppertal, Germany.

Table 3
Measures of statistical dispersion for image-based bikeability ratings.

Mean of...	Full sample	Bikeability class 1	Bikeability class 2	Bikeability class 3	Bikeability class 4	Bikeability class 5
Standard deviation	0.22	0.22	0.23	0.22	0.22	0.20
Mean absolute deviation (MAD)	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.17	0.18	0.15
Interquartile range (IQR)	0.28	0.28	0.30	0.28	0.30	0.24
Interdecile range	0.51	0.49	0.55	0.51	0.53	0.48
Median image rating	0.47	0.19	0.25	0.44	0.61	0.76

3.2.2. Summary of qualitative survey feedback

80 % of participants mentioned aspects they considered for bikeability ratings. 78 % of answers consider the presence of cars or traffic volume as a concern, 49 % refer to traffic speed. In 70 % of responses availability of bike infrastructure is mentioned, with 66 % preferring dedicated infrastructure to avoid mixing with cars. Quality of the road surface is mentioned in 43 % of answers, with 12 % highlighting the suitability of pavement for any weather condition. Aspects of the environment are present in 24 % of responses, with the majority (20 %) preferring green, natural surroundings. Road width is regarded in 16 % of answers. However, this aspect is controversial with neither too wide nor too narrow roads being favored. Multi-lane roads appear as deterrent in 26 % of responses. 39 % more generally refer to the availability of enough space for cycling as criterion. Potential conflicts through cyclists mixed with pedestrians (19 %), roadside parking (17 %), and presence of signage and ground markings (14 %) are further frequent mentions. Lighting (9 %), safety and security (7 %), visibility without occlusion (7 %), and noise (6 %) follow. Further mentions encompass the presence of heavy vehicles, distance to cars, and gradient.

Approximately half of the participants reported issues they encountered with rating bikeability from street-level imagery. The most frequently mentioned aspects concern estimating traffic volume (25 %), traffic speed (17 %), and the existence of separated bicycle infrastructure (15 %) from images. Non-visible (bicycle) signs were mentioned by 10 % of respondents. Further issues concern the type of traffic (e.g. heavy goods vehicles), lighting situation, separation from pedestrians, maintenance (throughout the year), (traffic) noise level, and identification of bicycle roads or similar mixed traffic concepts. While this work focused on segment-based bikeability, non-visibility of intersection details was reported by 16 % of respondents. Besides infrastructure-related aspects, 29 % of responses targeted the environment and soft external factors. Examples for this category are the time of day, local traffic culture, driver behavior, weather conditions, social safety, awareness of cyclists, liveliness, and availability of amenities. Furthermore, 7 % of answers refer to bikeability from a network perspective, regarding connectivity, continuity, and route quality as well as the availability of bicycle parking at origins and destinations.

Fig. 4. Image-based bikeability ratings and modelled bikeability (red line).

Fig. 5. Median of image-based ratings compared to modelled bikeability with linear regression.

Table 4
Comparison of classified bikeability: estimation vs. median ratings.

Classification	Same class [%]	Adjacent class [%]	Underestimated [%]	Overestimated [%]
5 classes	40.0	46.7	23.3	36.7
3 classes	61.7	36.7	8.3	30.0
2 classes	86.7	(13.3)	3.3	10.0

3.3. Expert workshop

We collected expert ratings and qualitative feedback within two identical expert workshops during the CRBAM, with approximately 40 participants in total. After the workshop we allowed all conference participants to rate the shown street-level images starting from a blank set of rating scales. Due to the open format, ratings were given individually and partly as the result of small group discussions.

3.3.1. Image-based assessment

Expert ratings collected throughout the CRBAM conference are presented in Fig. 6. On average, each street-level image received 22 ratings. Ratings for images 3 and 4 show high statistical dispersion (IQR 0.28 and 0.37), while dispersion is low for images 1 and 2 (IQR 0.08 and 0.10). Median values of the image ratings match the modelled bikeability class in 3 out of 5 cases, while the model over-estimated the remaining two cases.

Expert ratings show high similarity to online ratings, except to image 4. Here, the median of online ratings is 0.1 greater than the median of all conference ratings and 0.28 higher than workshop ratings only. Results for images 1 and 5 are nearly congruent, with delta of median ratings from 0.02 to 0.04. Deltas for images 2 and 3 range from 0.06 to 0.09. Images 1 and 2 have higher statistical dispersion in the survey compared to conference ratings. This is most pronounced for image 2.

For the first two images, negative aspects prevailed in expert feedback. The mixed traffic situation without dedicated bicycle

Fig. 6. Image-based expert ratings of bikeability (red line: modelled bikeability).

infrastructure was a main concern, especially in combination with high speed and expected high traffic volume (image 1). Consequently, image 1 was regarded dangerous for cyclists. For the second image, road and lane width were discussed controversially. Parked cars and the lack of a dooring zone were regarded dangerous. However, experts mentioned issues inferring the potential speed limit from image 2. Good road surface and flat terrain were positive attributes mentioned for both cases.

For the third example, experts regarded the speed limit of 30 km/h, greenery, and good road surface as positive aspects. While generally being perceived positive, the road width was seen as potential issue when cars meet. Parking was discussed controversially, including aspects such as sight impacts.

In contrast to modelled bikeability, image 4 received a lower median rating than image 3. Experts positively rated the presence of a bike lane, smooth pavement, and low traffic volume (local knowledge). The only negative aspect regarding the street segment concerned the presence of old markings alongside the newly painted dashed line. However, experts focused on the lack of continuity (ending bike lane) and problematic intersection design in their overall assessment, which is not captured by the segment-based approach.

The last image was regarded very bikeable by experts, highlighting absence of traffic or separated infrastructure, decent width, nice nature, and presence of a resting place. Absence of streetlights, mixing with pedestrians, and potential for cleaning were negatively remarked. Some experts stated issues with clearly detecting bicycle infrastructure or whether cars were allowed on this road from the image.

Full-size images and detailed expert feedback are provided in the supplementary materials.

3.3.2. Indicator ratings

Workshop participants added 13 indicators to our initial set of 7 model indicators. For further assessment within the scope of this paper we filtered out 5 indicators with less than five importance ratings by experts and 2 indicators that target connectivity and intersections. The highest importance (median of 80 % or higher) was attributed to *safe parking at night*, *bicycle infrastructure*, *car traffic volume*, and *maximum speed*. *Lighting*, *pavement*, *width for cycling together*, *gradient*, *tram tracks* and *natural environment* follow (median of 60 %-79 %). *Designated bike routes* and *streetside parking* are both attributed medium importance

(approx. 50 %). Only *road category* is seen as less important with a value of 27 %. Fig. 7 shows indicator ratings as well as relative indicator weights of our model.

The highest divergence between rated indicator importance and model indicator weight is present for road category, while the high relative importance and weight for bicycle infrastructure match well. Maximum speed, pavement and gradient are given higher importance by workshop participants compared to model indicator weights.

Ratings for designated route, road category and car parking show high statistical dispersion. High variation is also present for pavement and gradient. Regarding the indicators utilized by the default bikeability model, bicycle infrastructure and maximum speed show the lowest statistical dispersion, and both are considered as very important by the experts.

4. Discussion

Within this section, we discuss the results presented in Section 3. First, we regard the set of indicators as well as model parametrization. Second, we focus on the model outputs and address overall suitability of the model. In the last part we discuss limitations of the evaluation study and the proposed bikeability model.

4.1. Indicators and parameters

Indicator assessment within the expert workshop as well as qualitative feedback from the online survey reveal that presence and type of bicycle infrastructure, traffic volume, and maximum speed are among the most important indicators for segment-based bikeability. While bicycle infrastructure and maximum speed are used as indicators in our model, traffic volume is replaced by road category as a proxy. Surface quality, lighting, infrastructure width, gradient, presence of tram tracks, and natural environment are also considered important by experts, which aligns well with survey feedback. Out of them, surface quality and gradient are included in the default bikeability profile of the model. Greenness, proximity to water bodies and infrastructure width are available as optional indicators for custom profiles. Lighting and the presence of tram tracks in proximity to bicycle infrastructure are not yet implemented due to global availability and suitability of data.

Fig. 7. Indicator importance rated by experts and relative model weights (red line).

Designated cycling routes and car parking were attributed medium importance by experts. However, ratings showed high variation and both survey feedback as well as several experts emphasized the risks associated with streetside parking, such as dooring and lack of visibility. Streetside parking is currently implemented as a placeholder in the model, but not yet computed due to data issues. This is a main aspect for future improvement. Designated cycling routes serve as a proxy in our model to capture aspects such as signage for wayfinding, awareness of motorized traffic, as well as an expected minimum level of maintenance, overall quality, and continuity of infrastructure. All of these aspects were mentioned by participants in the qualitative part of the online survey. Safe (overnight) bike parking received high expert ratings but is not included in the bikeability model. Both safe overnight parking and lighting are examples for influencing aspects which may vary depending on time and purpose of a trip. These should be considered for future model improvement, given data availability.

Results of the online survey and expert feedback support the choice of core model indicators. We use road category as proxy mainly for traffic volume, which is regarded very important by experts and thus justifies the high relative weight. However, this may introduce uncertainty in cases of mismatch with traffic volume.

Results of the expert workshop show that relative importance of many indicators is regarded highly controversial. Still, results indicate that the weight for e.g. speed limit could be increased, and that additional indicators may further improve the model. The assessment of feasibility (regarding data availability), utility (increased complexity versus expected benefit) and transferability is up to future research.

In general, results of the online survey may be used to further calibrate model weights.

As an alternative to the knowledge-based, iterative approach for determining model parameters, findings from route choice modelling could be utilized. However, as Meister et al. (2024) found in a recent comparative study, model choice has significant impact on estimated effect size and Value-of-distance (VoD) indicators. Thus, the use of VoD indicators from a single route choice model for bikeability model parametrization appears questionable. However, the proposed knowledge-based approach makes explicit the need to critically reflect on (purpose-specific) model parametrization.

4.2. Model outputs

Model outputs for two sample areas show the feasibility of modelling segment-based bikeability from widely available open data sets. The evaluation study proved fitness of the model to estimate suitability of road segments for cycling in a generic way. This is based on ratings of 60 street-level images for a stratified random sample of locations across bikeability classes. However, results also indicate that the model tends to overestimate bikeability in several situations.

Human bikeability ratings are highly dispersed for many images, reflecting variation in individual preferences, assumptions, or purpose-specific considerations. This underlines the importance of adjustability and extendibility of the model. For 70 % of image samples modeled bikeability was within the mean absolute deviation of participant ratings. We focus on how well our model predicts the median of image ratings for assessing suitability of the generic bikeability profile. Strong correlation and low MAE indicate its suitability. This is supported by findings from binary classification of bikeability, in which case the model achieved 86.7 % of alignment with median ratings. Especially given the complexity and individuality of bikeability perception and the conceptual differences between data-driven modelling and image-based ratings, we regard these results as adequate for a generic bikeability model. Street-level imagery can reveal many additional aspects that are not represented in network data and vice versa. Examples for this are contained in qualitative feedback. Besides highlighting aspects which are not covered by the current model (partly by design), it can explain some of the differences between modelled and human-rated bikeability.

High statistical dispersion of ratings as well as partly controversially discussed aspects (e.g., road width) highlight the existence of diverse perceptions of bikeability. This emphasizes the need for open, adjustable, and extendible models that can represent such diversity in analyses and support the generation of scenarios. The proposed model meets these requirements due to the abstraction layer, which enables the use of various input data sets, as well as due to easy adaptability of parameters. For representing diversity, several bikeability assessments should be conducted per study area with different parameter sets which capture the bandwidth of local, purpose- and group-specific bikeability perceptions. This is a clear need for future research which can be informed by findings of the presented evaluation study.

Good alignment of survey responses with expert ratings indicates the utility of survey data for model validation. However, results noticeably

diverge for one image (wuppertal4i25) showing a bicycle lane that ends in front of a roundabout. Qualitative feedback reveals that the disutility of the shown infrastructure mainly concerns the ending bicycle infrastructure and intersection design. Divergence may be explained by differing focus being put on these issues relative to the remaining infrastructure of the road segment. This also serves as a good example where discrepancy between the segment-based bikeability model and image-based ratings occurs. As intersection design is not captured by the model yet, only the bicycle infrastructure along the segment is assessed. This might explain model overestimation in the specific case. However, not all cases of model overestimation can be traced back to this cause. Other factors such as data issues or aspects which are not modelled are expected to play a role. Further research is required to eliminate such problems and to increase the overall model performance. As the model is designed to be easily adjusted and extended, the foundation for such work is provided and further progress is to be expected.

4.3. Limitations

4.3.1. Evaluation study

The online survey is biased towards male respondents. Furthermore, most participants identified as 'enthused and confident', so barriers for less experienced cyclists might be underrepresented. It was beyond the scope of the evaluation study to address specific target groups. Austrian and German residents contributed the highest share of responses, potentially introducing regional bias. Consequently, differences in bikeability perception by country cannot reliably be assessed. Additionally, two survey participants commented that weather conditions visible on images might have influenced bikeability ratings. We cannot quantify the potential impact. However, we see that some images received very low bikeability ratings despite showing a scene in sunny weather. Presence of cars in street-level imagery is another aspect that might have influenced bikeability ratings. Due to random sampling of locations and images we did not actively control for it. All of these aspects contribute to the conceptual differences prevalent in bikeability ratings of street-level imagery compared to network-data-driven modelling. Furthermore, bikeability ratings based on street-level imagery may differ from ratings collected on site, when experiencing the infrastructure and environment live. Additionally, it was not feasible to represent all potential combinations of indicator values by sampled images. Therefore, quantitatively assessing the contribution of individual indicators to the model fit was impossible.

4.3.2. Bikeability model

Since the proposed bikeability model targets road segments, intersections and their specific designs are not covered. As these are known to be important regarding continuity, smoothness and overall safety of trips (e.g. Friel et al., 2023), future research should fill this gap.

The model abstracts reality based on indicators inferred from widely available open data. Quality of such data is vital. Regarding the dynamic genesis of OSM data, the model implementation may not fully cover all possible tag combinations. Furthermore, not all aspects considered important for specific purposes or infrastructure designs might be implemented in the default bikeability profile. However, the model is designed to be easily adjusted and extended.

5. Conclusions

This paper proposes a model to estimate segment-based bikeability from open data and assesses its suitability through an expert workshop and online survey. With the results presented and discussed in this paper, we can positively conclude on the research question that data-driven modelling of segment-based bikeability is feasible using open

data and the methodology outlined. Given the indicators considered, result evaluation, as well as its open, adjustable, and extensible implementation, the presented model advances the scientific state-of-the-art. While not all-encompassing, the evaluation study proved model applicability for generic bikeability assessments. It is transparent about its capabilities as well as limitations. We encourage interested readers to adapt the model for vulnerable road users and specific target groups in order to support a more inclusive mobility environment. The segment-based bikeability model has great potential in serving as foundation for more complex bikeability assessments that take into account relational, accessibility, and zonal aspects. Hence, it can improve transparency, reliability and inclusivity of methods that support decision making in urban and mobility planning.

The model is supposed to be continuously refined. Future research should assess preferences and requirements of vulnerable groups which currently are excluded from cycling mobility through presence of infrastructure barriers. Furthermore, spatial transferability and local specifics should be addressed. With integrating these aspects into bikeability models and planning processes, the highest potential for shifting towards sustainable mobility can be raised. Future work should also fill current (data) gaps in modelling temporary and micro-scale aspects. An especially limiting factor currently lies in data scarcity for modelling bikeability of intersections. All in all, we are convinced that open data, open research, and open-source software will help overcome the current limitations most efficiently and effectively.

Supplementary Resources

Software, Data, Images, and Results: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10724361>

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Christian Werner: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Lucas van der Meer:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation. **Dana Kaziyeva:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Petra Stutz:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Robin Wendel:** Methodology. **Martin Loidl:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

All data, code and results are available at: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10724361>

Acknowledgements

We thank everyone who contributed their time to make this research possible. Thank you to the experts who participated in our workshop at the CRBAM and gave feedback during the conference as well as to all participants of the online survey. We want to especially thank the anonymous reviewers of our manuscript for their valuable feedback. Furthermore, great thanks to all members of the PLUS Mobility Lab who were involved in the conception and implementation of the bikeability model over the years.

Appendix A. Full list of indicators

Table A1

Aspects, indicators, indicator values and their numerical mapping and weighting (default bikeability profile, including additional indicators)

theme	aspect of interest	indicator (observable, data item)	attribute values with default numerical mapping	default data source	default weight	remarks
safety, comfort	availability and type of bicycle infrastructure	bicycle infrastructure	bicycle way: 1 mixed way: 0.9 bicycle road: 0.85 cycletreet: 0.8 bicycle lane: 0.75 shared bus lane: 0.75 shared lane: 0.5 undefined: 0.2 no infra: 0	OpenStreetMap network geometry with attributes	0.2	
safety, comfort	signage, wayfinding, awareness of motorized traffic, min. level of quality	designated bicycle route	international: 1 national: 0.9 regional: 0.85 local: 0.8 unknown route: 0.8 no route: 0	OpenStreetMap cycle networks	0.1	
safety, comfort	traffic volume and potentially the share of HGV (heavy goods vehicles)	road category	primary: 0 path: 0 secondary: 0.2 residential: 0.8 service: 0.85 traffic calmed: 0.9 no motorized traffic: 1	OpenStreetMap network geometry with attributes	0.3	Please note: separated bicycle infrastructure parallel to e.g. a primary road will not bear the 'primary' attribute
safety, comfort	speed limit (of motorized traffic)	max. speed	≥ 100 km/h: 0 ≥ 80 km/h: 0.2 ≥ 70 km/h: 0.3 ≥ 60 km/h: 0.5 ≥ 50 km/h: 0.6 ≥ 30 km/h: 0.85 > 0 km/h: 0.9 0 km/h: 1	OpenStreetMap network geometry with attributes	0.1	
safety, comfort	potential of interaction with car parking (e.g. dooring)	car parking	yes: 0* no: 1*	OpenStreetMap (tbd.)*	0.1**	*this indicator cannot be reliably computed from available data sets (implementation is planned for future) **currently includes the indicator as placeholder
safety, comfort	surface quality	pavement type	asphalt: 1 gravel: 0.75 soft surface: 0.4 cobble stone: 0	OpenStreetMap network geometry with attributes	0.1*	*weight is increased in case of gravel combined with steep gradient
safety, comfort	width of road or bicycle infrastructure	width	≥ 5 m: 1 ≥ 4 m: 0.9 ≥ 3 m: 0.85 ≥ 2 m: 0.5 ≥ 0 m: 0	OpenStreetMap network geometry with attributes	-	currently only implemented for metric units
safety, comfort	steepness of the road or path: safety aspects and physical effort needed	gradient (difference in elevation between nodes of each edge)	≥ 12 %: 0 < 12 %: 0.25 < 6 %: 0.4 < 3 %: 0.5 < 1.5 %, > -1.5 %: 0.9 > -3 %: 1 > -6 %: 0.95 > -12 %: 0.35 ≤ -12 %: 0	OpenStreetMap network geometry and digital elevation model (DEM)	0.1*	[optional] *weight is increased in case of gravel combined with steep gradient
safety, comfort	traffic volume and complexity (parallel traffic, switching lanes, turns, etc.)	number of lanes	> 4: 0 > 3: 0.1 > 2: 0.2 > 1: 0.5 > 0: 1	OpenStreetMap network geometry with attributes	-	
environment	points of interest in proximity	facilities	> 0: 1 = 0: 0	OpenStreetMap	-	based on count per 100 m (30 m buffer)
environment	density of built environment	building ratio	≥ 80 %: 0 ≥ 60 %: 0.2 ≥ 40 %: 0.4 ≥ 20 %: 0.6	OpenStreetMap	-	intersection of building footprints with 20 m buffer

(continued on next page)

Table A1 (continued)

theme	aspect of interest	indicator (observable, data item)	attribute values with default numerical mapping	default data source	default weight	remarks
environment	greenness of surrounding	greenness ratio	> 0 %: 0.8 = 0 %: 1 > 75 %: 1 > 50 %: 0.9 > 25 %: 0.8 > 0 %: 0.7 = 0 %: 0	OpenStreetMap	-	uses 30 m buffer
environment	proximity to water bodies	presence of water bodies	yes: 1 no: 0	OpenStreetMap	-	uses 30 m buffer
comfort, environment	exposure to traffic noise	noise levels [dB]	> 70: 0 > 55: 0.6 > 10: 0.8 ≥ 0: 1	Traffic noise polygons (open government data e. g. in Austria)	-	[optional]

For further details and explanation of indicator values please refer to the online documentation of [NetAScore](#)

*Please find all remarks in the right-hand column for each indicator

Appendix B. Detailed plots: modelled bikeability in relation to survey ratings

In the following plots, all survey ratings are visualized as box plot per image sample. The modelled bikeability value is shown as red line. Additionally, the respective street-level images are provided. Full-size images and detail plots for all images shown in the online survey are contained in the supplementary materials.

By response variability

Fig. B1. Bikeability ratings for the five samples with highest response variability (IQR).

Fig. B2. Bikeability ratings for the five samples with lowest response variability (IQR).

By deviation from median rating

Fig. B3. Bikeability for the five samples with lowest absolute deviation from median rating.

Fig. B4. Bikeability for the five samples with highest absolute deviation from median rating.

References

- Arellana, J., Saltarín, M., Larrañaga, A.M., González, V.I., Henao, C.A., 2020. Developing an urban bikeability index for different types of cyclists as a tool to prioritise bicycle infrastructure investments. *Transp. Res. Part A: Policy Pract.* 139, 310–334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2020.07.010>.
- Bergische Universität Wuppertal. (2023). *CRBAM 2023* (Wuppertal). (<https://radverkehr.uni-wuppertal.de/en/crbam-2023/>) (last accessed on January 12, 2024).
- Beura, S.K., Srivastava, A., Bhuyan, P.K., 2021. Unsignalized intersection level of service: a bicyclist's perspective. *Int. J. Intell. Transp. Syst. Res.* 19 (2), 405–416. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13177-020-00244-z>.
- Broach, J., Dill, J., Gliebe, J., 2012. Where do cyclists ride? A route choice model developed with revealed preference GPS data. *Transp. Res. Part A: Policy Pract.* 46 (10), 1730–1740. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2012.07.005>.
- Buehler, R., Dill, J., 2016. Bikeway Networks: A Review of Effects on Cycling. *Transp. Rev.* 36 (1), 9–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2015.1069908>.
- Callister, D., Lowry, M., 2013. Tools and strategies for wide-scale bicycle level-of-service analysis. *J. Urban Plan. Dev.* 139 (4), 250–257. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)UP.1943-5444.0000159](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)UP.1943-5444.0000159).
- Castañon, U.N., Ribeiro, P.J.G., 2021. Bikeability and emerging phenomena in cycling: exploratory analysis and review. Article 4. *Sustainability* 13 (4) <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13042394>.
- Codina, O., Maciejewska, M., Nadal, J., Marquet, O., 2022. Built environment bikeability as a predictor of cycling frequency: lessons from Barcelona. *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.* 16, 100725 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2022.100725>.
- Friel, D., Wachholz, S., Werner, T., Zimmermann, L., Schwedes, O., Stark, R., 2023. Cyclists' perceived safety on intersections and roundabouts – a qualitative bicycle simulator study. *J. Saf. Res.* 87, 143–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsr.2023.09.012>.
- Geller, R. (2009). *Four types of cyclists*. PortlandOnline. <https://www.portland-oregon.gov/transportation/article/158497> (last accessed on January 6, 2020).
- Grigore, E., Garrick, N., Fuhrer, R., Axhausen, Ing K.W., 2019. Bikeability in Basel, 0361198119839982 *Transp. Res. Rec.* <https://doi.org/10.1177/0361198119839982>.
- Hagen, O.H., Rynning, M.K., 2021. Promoting cycling through urban planning and development: a qualitative assessment of bikeability. *Urban, Plan. Transp. Res.* 9 (1), 276–305. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21650020.2021.1938195>.
- Hamidi, Z., Camporeale, R., Caggiani, L., 2019. Inequalities in access to bike-and-ride opportunities: findings for the city of Malmö. *Transp. Res. Part A: Policy Pract.* 130, 673–688. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2019.09.062>.
- Hardinghaus, M., Nieland, S., Lehne, M., Weschke, J., 2021. More than bike lanes—a multifactorial index of urban bikeability. Article 21. *Sustainability* 13 (21) <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132111584>.
- Hardinghaus, M., Weschke, J., 2022. Attractive infrastructure for everyone? Different preferences for route characteristics among cyclists. *Transp. Res. Part D: Transp. Environ.* 111, 103465 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2022.103465>.
- Highway Capacity Manual. (2010). Transportation research board of the national academies. *Washington, DC*, 2010.
- Kamel, M.B., Sayed, T., Bigazzi, A., 2020. A composite zonal index for biking attractiveness and safety. *Accid. Anal. Prev.* 137, 105439 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2020.105439>.
- Karolemeas, C., Vassi, A., Tsigdinos, S., Bakogiannis, Dr.E., 2022. Measure the ability of cities to be biked via weighted parameters, using GIS tools. The case study of Zografou in Greece. *Transp. Res. Procedia* 62, 59–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2022.02.008>.
- Kellstedt, D.K., Spengler, J.O., Foster, M., Lee, C., Maddock, J.E., 2021. A scoping review of bikeability assessment methods. *J. Community Health* 46 (1), 211–224. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10900-020-00846-4>.
- Krenn, P.J., Oja, P., Titze, S., 2015. Development of a bikeability index to assess the bicycle-friendliness of urban environments. *Open J. Civ. Eng.* 05 (04), 451–459. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojce.2015.54045>.
- Land Kärnten - data.gv.at (2019). *Digital Elevation Modell (DEM) Austria* (b5de6975-417b-4320-afdb-eb2a9e2a1dbf) [GeoTIFF]. <https://www.data.gv.at/katalog/en/dataset/b5de6975-417b-4320-afdb-eb2a9e2a1dbf>.
- Lee, C.-F., 2014. An investigation of factors determining cycling experience and frequency. *Tour. Geogr.* 16 (5), 844–862. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616688.2014.927524>.
- Loidl, M., Zagel, B., 2014. Assessing bicycle safety in multiple networks with different data models. *GI-Forum. Salzburg* 144–154.
- Lowry, M.B., Callister, D., Gresham, M., Moore, B., 2012. Assessment of communitywide bikeability with bicycle level of service. *Transp. Res. Rec.* 2314 (1), 41–48. <https://doi.org/10.3141/2314-06>.
- Mapillary A.B. (n.d.). *Mapillary*. Retrieved January 12, 2024, from <https://www.mapillary.com/app/>.
- Meister, A., Liang, Z., Felder, M., Axhausen, K.W., 2024. Comparative study of route choice models for cyclists. *J. Cycl. Micro Res.* 2, 100018 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcjr.2024.100018>.
- Mekuria, M., Furth, P., & Nixon, H. (2012). *Low-Stress Bicycling and Network Connectivity*. *Mineta Transportation Institute Publications*. http://scholarworks.sjsu.edu/mti_publications/74.
- Mertens, L., Compernelle, S., Deforche, B., Mackenbach, J.D., Lakerveld, J., Brug, J., Roda, C., Feuillet, T., Oppert, J.-M., Glonti, K., Rutter, H., Bardos, H., De Bourdeaudhuij, I., Van Dyck, D., 2017. Built environmental correlates of cycling for transport across Europe. *Health Place* 44, 35–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthplace.2017.01.007>.
- Munira, S., Sener, I.N., Zhang, Y., 2021. Estimating bicycle demand in the austin, texas area: role of a bikeability index. *J. Urban Plan. Dev.* 147 (3), 04021036 [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)UP.1943-5444.0000725](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)UP.1943-5444.0000725).
- Open.NRW. (2023). *Digitales Geländemodell NW Gitterweite 1m* (digitales-gelandemodell-nw-gitterweite-1mea468) [WCS]. <https://www.govdata.de/web/guest/suchen/>. https://www.wcs.nrw.de/geobasis/wcs_nw_dgm?REQUEST=GetCapabilities&SERVICE=WCS.
- Pais, F., Monteiro, J., Sousa, N., Coutinho-Rodrigues, J., Natividade-Jesus, E., 2022. A multicriteria methodology for maintenance planning of cycling infrastructure.

- Proc. Inst. Civ. Eng. - Eng. Sustain. 175 (5), 248–264. <https://doi.org/10.1680/jensu.21.00088>.
- Porter, A.K., Kohl, H.W., Pérez, A., Reininger, B., Pettee Gabriel, K., Salvo, D., 2019. Bikeability: assessing the objectively measured environment in relation to recreation and transportation bicycling. 0013916518825289 Environ. Behav.. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916518825289>.
- Psarrou Kalakoni, A.M., Christoforou, Z., Farhi, N., 2022. A novel methodology for micromobility system assessment using multi-criteria analysis. Case Stud. Transp. Policy 10 (2), 976–992. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cstp.2022.03.010>.
- Raifer, M. (n.d.). *Overpass turbo*. Retrieved January 12, 2024, from <https://overpass-turbo.eu/>.
- Redfin Corporation. (n.d.). *Bike Score Methodology*. Retrieved January 10, 2024, from <https://www.walkscore.com/bike-score-methodology.shtml>.
- Santos, B., Passos, S., Gonçalves, J., Matias, I., 2022. Spatial multi-criteria analysis for road segment cycling suitability assessment. Article 16. Sustainability 14 (16) <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14169928>.
- Schmid-Querg, J., Keler, A., Grigoropoulos, G., 2021. The munich bikeability index: a practical approach for measuring urban bikeability. Article 1. Sustainability 13 (1) <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13010428>.
- Sorton, A., Walsh, T., 1994. Bicycle stress level as a tool to evaluate urban and suburban bicycle compatibility. Transp. Res. Rec. 17–17.
- Sottile, E., Sanjust di Teulada, B., Meloni, I., Cherchi, E., 2019. Estimation and validation of hybrid choice models to identify the role of perception in the choice to cycle. Int. J. Sustain. Transp. 13 (8), 543–552. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15568318.2018.1490465>.
- Tijana, D., Tomić, N., Tešić, D., 2023. Walkability and bikeability for sustainable spatial planning in the city of novi sad (Serbia). Article 4. Sustainability 15 (4) <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15043785>.
- Werner, C., Wendel, R., Kaziyeva, D., Stutz, P., van der Meer, L., Zagel, B., Loidl, M., 2024. plus- mobilitylab/netascore: V1.0.1-fix (v1.0.1-fix) [Computer software]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666445>.
- Wesener, A., Vallance, S., Tesch, M., Edwards, S., Frater, J., Moreham, R., 2021. A mobile sense of place: exploring a novel mixed methods user-centred approach to capturing data on urban cycling infrastructure. Appl. Mobilities 0 (0), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23800127.2021.1893941>.
- Winters, M., Teschke, K., Brauer, M., Fuller, D., 2016. Bike Score®: associations between urban bikeability and cycling behavior in 24 cities. Int. J. Behav. Nutr. Phys. Act. 13, 18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-016-0339-0>.
- Wysling, L., Purves, R.S., 2022. Where to improve cycling infrastructure? Assessing bicycle suitability and bikeability with open data in the city of Paris. Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect. 15, 100648 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2022.100648>.
- Yang, Y., Wu, X., Zhou, P., Gou, Z., Lu, Y., 2019. Towards a cycling-friendly city: an updated review of the associations between built environment and cycling behaviors (2007–2017). J. Transp. Health 14, 100613. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2019.100613>.